

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

KAU170, a promising short-duration rice variety resistant to brown planthopper (BPH)

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BPH was a serious problem in Kuttanad from 1973 to 1974. A hybridization program was started at RRS in 1976 to develop a BPH-resistant, short-duration variety using locally accepted modem varieties and BPH-resistant, tall varieties, such as Ptb 33 and ARC6650.

KAU170 from the cross ARC6650/Jaya performed well in trials for yield and pest resistance. KAU170 (IET9268) was released in 1990 as Makam (MO 9) for use during the three seasons in Kerala. It is a short-duration (110 d), dwarf (75-80 cm) variety with red kernels, short bold grains, resistance to BPH, and seed dormancy of 2 wk.

KAU170 performed well against locally accepted modem varieties in many field trials at numerous locations (see table). When screened for pests and diseases, it showed moderate resistance to sheath blight, sheath rot, stem borer, gall midge, and leafhopper. □

Performance of Makam in yield trials.

Trial and location	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Makam	Check variety ^a
RRS field trial, Moncompu, 1983-84	5.6	4.9
Multilocation trial, 1983 (12 locations)	3.7	3.4
Multilocation trial, 1984 (10 locations)	6.1	5.4
All India Coordinated trials Brown Planthopper Resistant Variety Trial (BPHRVT), 1988 (11 locations)	4.2	3.3
Farm trials, 1987-88 (10 locations)	3.6	2.7

^aJyothi at RRS, Moncompu, multilocation and farm trials, and MR1523 for BPHRVT.

Performance of Mukthi (CTH1) in coastal Karnataka, India

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The coastal zone of Karnataka is a narrow strip of land lying between the Arabian Sea on the west and the Western Ghats on the east. Rice is cultivated on about 0.2 million ha during three cropping seasons. Rainfall averages around 4,000 mm, the majority of which falls during kharif (Jun-Sep) when mostly rainfed rice is grown. Rice is an irrigated crop during winter (Oct-Jan).

Mukthi is a red-kerneled, high-yielding variety with cold tolerance and blast resistance recommended for southern Karnataka. It is well-suited to winter. Its performance in the coastal zone has been studied during rabi (dry season) under irrigated conditions in lowland farming situations.

In field trials at the Regional Research Station, Brahmavar, and the Agricultural Research Station, Kankanady, during 1989-90 and 1990-91, Mukthi consistently yielded 16% more than the local check Shakti, a

Table 1. Yield of Mukthi (CTH1) in coastal Karnataka, India.

Location	Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Mukthi	Check (Shakti)
Regional Research Station, Brahmavar, 1989-90, 1990-91	Red rice varietal trial	4.1	3.2
	Blast tolerance varietal trial	3.8	3.6
	Mid-duration varietal trial	5.2	4.9
Agricultural Research Station, Kankanady RRS, Brahmavar, 1990-91	Uniform varietal trial	4.1	3.6
	Demonstration plot	3.8	3.2
	Mean	4.2	3.7

high-yielding, recommended variety for the zone (Table 1). Mukthi also resisted diseases better than Shakti (Table 2).

Mukthi is potentially suitable for the rabi crop of the coastal region of Karnataka. □

Table 2. Reaction^a of Mukthi (CTH1) to diseases in coastal Karnataka.^b

Variety	Leaf spot ^b	Leaf blast ^b	Neck blast (%)
Mukthi	3.4	2.3	1.7
Shakti	3.9	2.7	3.2

^aMean of 4 trials. ^bScored with the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) on a scale of 0.9.

Remya—a new brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant, medium-duration variety from Kerala

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BPH is a threat to rice production in Kerala, especially in Kuttanad, which is a unique delta area with 52,000 ha of riceland, 0.5-2.0 m below sea level. Wet

season (Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr) rice harvest coincides with the monsoon. Rice grains often germinate on the panicle before harvest. BPH has become endemic because of the warm, humid conditions. Kuttanad farmers use modem varieties, none of which have seed dormancy and BPH resistance.

Remya (MO 10)—culture KAU126 (IET9266), derived from the cross Jaya/Ptb 33—was released by RRS in 1990. Remya is a medium-duration (120 d), BPH-resistant variety with seed dormancy of up to 1 mo. It has red

Table 1. Remya (Mo 10) yields in Kerala, India.

	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Remya	Check variety ^b
RRS, Moncompu (field trials)	5.1	4.5
Multilocation trials 1983-84 wet season (5 locations)	6.8	5.4
All India Coordinated trials BPHRVT, 1984 dry season (11 locations)	4.9	3.3
BPHRVT, 1985 dry season (8 locations)	4.6	3.2
Farm trials 1988-89, 2 seasons (7 locations)	5.0	4.2

^a BPHRVT = Brown Planthopper Resistant Variety Trial.
^b Jaya for research station and multilocation trials, MR1523 for BPHRVT 1984, IET7575 for BPHRVT 1985, and Pavizham for farm trial.

Table 2. Remya reaction^a to pests and diseases at RRS, Moncompu, India.

Variety	Sheath blight	Sheath rot	Blast	Brown spot		Gall midge	BPH
				Leaf	Grain		
Remya	1.4	3.0	1.0	1.0	1.2	3.0	2.3
TNI	2.8	3.2	5.0	1.2	4.4	5.0	9.0

^a Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0-9.

kernels and long bold grains which are qualities preferred by Keralites. It is semitall (100-110 cm).

In field and multilocation trials in 1983-84, it outyielded the check variety Jaya (Table 1). In All India Coordinated yield trials it ranked second out of 54 entries in 1984; in 1985, it ranked 7th out

of 50 entries. In farm trials during 1988-89, it outyielded the check variety in seven locations. Reactions to different pests and diseases are presented in Table 2.

Remya is recommended for all three seasons in Kerala. □

RCPL 1-1C, a cold-tolerant rice for high-altitude areas of Meghalaya, India

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Suboptimal temperature at reproductive phase, neck blast, and sheath rot are the major constraints to increasing rice production in high-altitude areas of NEH in India. Many exotic and indigenous lines from the National Cold Tolerance Nursery and the International

Table 1. Yield of RCPL 1-1C in Upper Shillong, India, 1985-90.

Cultivar	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	1985	1986 ^a	1987	1988	1989	1990
RCPL 1-1C	2.3	1.6	3.6	4.2	2.8	3.1
Khonorullo	1.9	1.3	2.9	3.3	2.1	2.5
Increase over check (%)	22	25	24	28	25	16

^aSevere rat damage (>50%).

Table 2. Yield of RCPL 1-1C in 2 farmers' fields in Meghalaya.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Mylliem (1700 m)	Sohiong (1650 m)
RCPL 1-1C	2.9	2.3
Khonorullo	1.7	2.0

Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were evaluated at various growth stages. Most of them either exhibited poor spikelet fertility or did not set seed at all. Even the well-known cold-tolerant cultivars Stejaree 45, Barkat, Eiko, K39, K332, and CH1039 exhibited high spikelet sterility (>80%). Local cultivars, however, possess cold tolerance and have low spikelet sterility (<30%).

ICAR has developed a new line, RCPL 1-1C, at the experimental farm of Upper Shillong (1,850 mean sea level [msl], 25°32'N, 91°51'E), where average minimum and maximum temperatures are 11 and 19 °C at seedling stage, 15 and 20 °C at tillering and panicle initiation, and 9 and 18 °C at ripening. These temperatures are suboptimum for rice growth. Soil of the experimental area is loam with pH 5-4, 5.5% organic C, 11.8% clay, 46.3 ppm available P, and CEC 24.5 meq.

RCPL 1-1C, derived from Pusa 331 Khonorullo, is a cold-tolerant, high-

yielding indica rice. It matures in 165 d at high altitude (>1,300 msl), has moderate tillering (5-6) and semidwarf stature (90-95 cm), and is tolerant of low temperature (15-20°C) and short daylength (2-2.5 h sunlight/d) at the reproductive phase. It is also moderately tolerant of cold at the vegetative phase.

Kernels are medium slender and red. It has 1,000-grain weight of 22-23 g, and moderate resistance to blast and sheath rot. Yields range from 3 to 3.5 t/ha. Its spikelet sterility is very low (<20%) at optimum transplanting time (1st week of June) but becomes higher (40-50%) with later transplanting (up to last week of June).

In on-farm trials during 1985-90, mean yield was 2.3-4.2 t grain/ha, showing an advantage of 16-28% over Khonorullo, a local cold-tolerant cultivar (Table 1). It also did well in farmers' fields in adaptive trials in Meghalaya (Table 2). □

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.